

Reverse Genetic Analysis on Role of BDNF in Hippocampal Function and Memory

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Introduction

Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (*BDNF*) is a neurotrophin that plays a fundamental role in the development, survival, and function of neurons in the central nervous system. It is highly expressed in the hippocampus, a brain region critical for spatial learning, memory formation, and synaptic plasticity (Lu et al., 2021). *BDNF* regulates multiple cellular processes, including dendritic spine growth, synaptic organization, and long-term potentiation (LTP)—a mechanism essential for strengthening synaptic connections during memory consolidation (Lu et al., 2020). Studies show that *BDNF* enhances synaptic responses in a dose-dependent manner and promotes long-lasting increases in synaptic transmission, highlighting its role as a key molecular mediator of hippocampal-dependent learning and memory processes (Lu et al., 2021).

The hippocampus is a core structure for encoding and retrieving spatial and episodic memory (Lu et al., 2021). In particular, tasks like the Morris Water Maze (MWM) and conditioned fear memory tests depend heavily on hippocampal function (Hernández-Mercado & Zepeda, 2022). Studies have shown that *BDNF* expression correlates with performance in these tasks, as it supports synaptic plasticity and neurogenesis (Huo et al., 2021). Decreased *BDNF* levels impair LTP, resulting in poor spatial navigation and reduced cognitive flexibility in rodent models (Huo et al., 2021). Conversely, higher *BDNF* levels enhance memory formation and resilience to age-related cognitive decline (Zhou et al., 2017). This has positioned *BDNF* as a critical focus for studying learning, memory, and neurodegenerative disorders.

Beyond its role in basic neuroscience, *BDNF* has significant translational implications for general health and disease. Reduced *BDNF* levels are associated with neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, where impaired synaptic plasticity leads to progressive memory loss (Bathina & Das, 2015). In addition, *BDNF* dysregulation has been implicated in psychiatric disorders, including depression and anxiety, where it contributes to cognitive deficits and emotional dysfunction (Bathina & Das, 2015). Therapeutic strategies aimed at increasing *BDNF* expression are being explored as potential treatments for these conditions.

This analysis focuses on *BDNF* expression in the hippocampus across BXD strains. The hippocampus was the chosen tissue of interest due to its well-established role in learning and memory, as well as its sensitivity to *BDNF*-mediated signaling pathways. By correlating *BDNF* expression levels with conditioned fear memory performance in mice fed a chow diet, the relationship between *BDNF* expression and hippocampal-dependent associative learning can be investigated.

Data Figures

Figure 1. BDNF transcription levels across various strains of BXD *Mus musculus*. This bar graph shows the variation in *BDNF* expression (probe 1422168_a_at) across 71 BXD strains in hippocampus mRNA, as measured by log₂-transformed expression values. Error bars represent standard deviations, reflecting variability within each strain. The data were derived from the Hippocampus Consortium M430v2 (Jun06) RMA dataset. The results highlight significant genetic variability in *BDNF* expression levels, which may underlie differences in hippocampal function and memory-related phenotypes among the strains.

Correlation Between BDNF (1422168_a_at) and Epha4 (1421929_at) Expression in the Hippocampus

X axis: [mouse BXD Hippocampus mRNA HC_M2_0606_R: 1421929_at](#)
[Epha4 on Chr1: 77.373757 Mb] Eph receptor A4; last three exons

Y axis: [mouse BXD Hippocampus mRNA HC_M2_0606_R: 1422168_a_at](#)
[Bdnf on Chr2: 109.723659 Mb] brain derived neurotrophic factor; distal half of last exon (coding sequence, common to both somatic and dendritic isoforms)

Figure 2. Scatterplot showing Pearson Correlation Analysis between *BDNF* expression (1422168_a_at) and *Epha4* expression (probe 1421929_at) in the hippocampus across 99 BXD strains.

X axis: [mouse BXD BXDPublish: 19116](#)

[PubMed: 2019](#) Central nervous system, behavior: Conditioned fear memory (CFM), freezing in response to 10 min contextual fear memory test in wildtype non-transgenic B6-BXD F1 males and females at 14 months-of-age on normal chow diet (all Nash Annex cases) [percent]

Y axis: [mouse BXD Hippocampus mRNA HC_M2_0606_R: 1422168_a_at](#)

[Bdnf on Chr2: 109.723659 Mb] brain derived neurotrophic factor; distal half of last exon (coding sequence, common to both somatic and dendritic isoforms)

Figure 3. Pearson Correlation Analysis between *BDNF* expression levels and conditioned fear memory performance in BXD mouse strains.

Figure 4. Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis of biological processes for the top 500 genes correlated with BDNF using WebGestalt. Enrichment significance is represented by False Discovery Rate (FDR), with all processes shown having an $FDR \leq 0.05$.

Results

Variation in *BDNF* Expression Across BXD Strains

The variation in *BDNF* expression was analyzed using the Hippocampus Consortium M430v2 (Jun06) RMA dataset. The expression levels – measured as log₂-transformed values – were assessed across 71 different BXD strains. The results – as seen in Figure 1 revealed significant variability, with the highest levels observed in BXD64 (10.4) and the lowest in BXD45 (8.5), reflecting a 20.1% difference in transcription levels which reflects genetic diversity across BXD mouse strains that influence hippocampal function. A Q-Q plot confirmed that the data closely approximates a normal distribution, with slight deviation. This variation highlights the genetic regulation of *BDNF* expression within the BXD population, which makes it a suitable candidate for investigating its association with hippocampal function and memory phenotypes.

Correlation Between *BDNF* and *Epha4* Expression

A scatter plot Pearson's analysis was conducted to examine the correlation between *BDNF* expression and *Epha4* expression in the hippocampus across the 99 BXD mouse strain; as seen in Figure 2. The results indicated a strong positive correlation with a Pearson correlation coefficient of $r = 0.618$ ($p < 0.001$). *EphA4* contributes to neural connectivity by mediating axon repulsion and synapse maturation, while *BDNF* enhances synaptic plasticity and long-term potentiation, critical for cognitive processes like memory consolidation (Kania & Klein, 2016). These complementary roles suggest a potential interaction between *EphA4* and *BDNF* in shaping hippocampal structure and function, which is vital for learning and memory (Klein, 2020; Kowalski et al., 2019). The regression analysis produced the line $y = 0.581x + 3.418$ and the strong correlation suggests that *BDNF* and *Epha4* are co-regulated; likely through shared molecular pathways involved in axon guidance and synaptic plasticity. Additionally, these pathways play critical roles in hippocampal structure and function, further emphasizing the importance of *BDNF* in processes like learning and memory.

Correlation Between *BDNF* Expression and Conditioned Fear Memory

Figure 3 shows the relationship between *BDNF* expression levels – from the Hippocampus Consortium M430v2 (Jun06) RMA dataset – and conditioned fear memory performance from the BXD Publish dataset, which measures the freezing percentage in response to a contextual fear conditioning test, a hippocampal-dependent learning task. The Pearson correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.482$, $p = 0.027$, $n = 21$), suggesting that higher *BDNF* transcription levels are associated with improved hippocampal-dependent memory performance, which is reflected by increased freezing behavior; however, given the moderate correlation coefficient, it can be attributed to additional genes or external/environmental factors that contribute to conditioned fear memory performance; as seen

in **Figure 2**. These findings align with BDNF's well-established role in supporting synaptic plasticity, neurogenesis, and long-term potentiation (LTP), which are critical for memory formation and hippocampal-dependent cognitive functions.

Gene Ontology Analysis through WebGestalt

Figure 4 summarizes the findings from a Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis of the top 500 genes correlated with BDNF using WebGestalt. The analysis reveals significant enrichment in biological processes such as postsynaptic organization, dendritic morphogenesis, synapse assembly, and synaptic signaling. These processes are critical for maintaining neuronal connectivity, enhancing synaptic plasticity, and supporting neurogenesis in the hippocampus. The findings suggest that BDNF transcription is intricately linked with pathways regulating synaptic transmission and dendritic development, which are essential for learning and memory. These results underscore BDNF's central role in neural plasticity, cognitive resilience, and its potential involvement in memory-related disorders.

Conclusion and Future Directions

The findings from this analysis highlights the critical role of *Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF)* in hippocampal function and its contribution to memory-related phenotypes. The variation in *BDNF* expression across BXD strains demonstrates genetic regulation (**Figure 1**), which correlates with both gene expression (*Epha4*; Figure 2) and behavior (conditioned fear memory; Figure 3). The positive correlation between *BDNF* and *Epha4* ($r = 0.618$, $p < 0.001$) implies a shared role in molecular pathways, such as axonal guidance and synaptic plasticity, which are crucial processes for hippocampal connectivity. Similarly, the correlation between *BDNF* and improved memory performance ($r = 0.482$, $p = 0.027$) reinforces its importance in learning and memory by supporting synaptic plasticity, long-term potentiation (LTP), and neurogenesis.

To validate these findings, future studies should employ experimental models to explore the causal relationship between *BDNF* and the observed phenotypes. One approach would involve generating *BDNF* knockout (KO) mice to investigate the impact of *BDNF* deficiency on hippocampal-dependent tasks such as the MWZ or contextual fear conditioning (Lu et al., 2021). Based on the BXD results, it can be expected that *BDNF* KO mice would exhibit impaired memory performance, reduced synaptic plasticity, and altered gene expression profiles, such as a decrease in *Epha4*. Complementary overexpression models could further confirm whether increased *BDNF* levels enhance memory performance and neuronal plasticity, providing direct evidence of its functional role.

Cell culture models could also be used to study the molecular connections of BDNF and *Epha4*. Primary hippocampal neurons produced from BXD strains with different BDNF expression levels could be grown and controlled using inhibitors or overexpression constructs.

Co-culture research could investigate how changing Epha4 expression affects synaptic plasticity or structural dynamics in response to BDNF, thereby explaining their shared routes.

Additionally, advanced techniques such as RNA sequencing or proteomics in KO or overexpression models could help identify downstream targets and pathways regulated by BDNF. This would provide new insights into the gene networks and cellular processes that drive memory formation and cognitive resilience. Exploring these pathways in neurodegenerative conditions, where BDNF expression is frequently dysregulated, could result in new therapeutic approaches for diseases such as Alzheimer's and age-related cognitive decline.

All in all, this study identifies BDNF as a vital regulator of hippocampal-dependent learning and memory. Future experimental validation implementing animal models and in vitro systems will corroborate the findings from the BXD analysis while also revealing the molecular mechanisms by which BDNF and its associated pathways influence cognitive processes. These findings will lay the groundwork for possible treatment strategies that target BDNF to improve memory and learning in both healthy and diseased individuals.

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